

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Exploring Data Augmentation Techniques for Sound Event Detection

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Dedication

Omnia aliena sunt, tempus tantum nostrum est., Lucio Anneo Seneca

Abstract

Everyday environments are overflowed with a wide variety of acoustic events, either produced by humans, animals, or objects. The identification of the class of a sound and its relative persistency time boundaries can open several opportunities and applications in different fields such as smart homes, autonomous cars, smart cities, industrial fault detection, surveillance systems, and healthcare. Therefore, *Sound Event Detection* (SED) systems have gained great attention in the past few years, especially driven by the new opportunities coming from the application of different types of Neural Networks (NNs) to the SED task. The performances of these systems can heavily depend on the availability of a large amount of strongly labeled data especially for model training. Gathering or retrieving this data is often difficult and costly. Synthetic data frequently offer a solution to increase the availability of information but they can lead the model to face overfitting problems. The objective of this work is to explore, combine and compare different data augmentation (DA) techniques to balance out the lack of strongly labeled data and to mitigate the possible overfitting scenario introduced by the use of synthetic data. For the aim of this investigation, the *Detection and Classification of Acoustic Scenes and Events* (DCASE) Challenge 2022 has been chosen as a laboratory for DA methods exploration. As an additional contribution, the best result has been submitted to the Task4 of the challenge.

The first part of the manuscript provides a brief introduction followed by an overview of the state-of-art of the SED systems and their relative data augmentation techniques. Secondly, the experiment strategy and methodology are presented. Finally, all results are reported and documented introducing the possible future contributions.

Keywords: Sound Event Detection; Data Augmentation; DCASE

Chapter 1

Introduction

Our everyday environment includes a wide range of different sounds to which we are continuously exposed. The set of all these acoustic events creates a quite complex polyphonic auditory scene that allows our brain to gather a huge amount of feedback and information about what surrounds us. The human auditory system is able to efficiently process these complex acoustic scenes making it possible to discriminate, localize and identify the different sounds. In the case of speech sounds, in particular, human perception results highly specialized in focusing the attention on the sound source of interest. This phenomenon is called the *cocktail party effect* and it was already described in 1953 by a study conducted by Cherry [6]. We can easily deduce that in the case that the subject of recognition is an automatic system, we will face several challenges and complexities.

1.1 Sound Event Detection systems

As described in an exhaustive tutorial published by Mesaros et al.[20], the goal of an automatic Sound Event Detection (SED) system can be defined as the recognition of what is happening within an audio signal and when it is happening. In other words, given an auditory scene and its relative audio signal, the purpose of a SED system is to recognize at what temporal instances different sound classes are active. The concept is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Sound Event Detection task

SED systems are widely used for many different applications as, for instance, automatic surveillance [13][2], multimedia events detection [36], smart rooms [5], biodiversity monitoring [18], autonomous driving vehicles[32], anomalous sound detection [21] or home automation and healthcare [1]. Like many other of audio research fields, the dominant recent approaches used to tackle the SED task is based on supervised learning [19], where a training set of audio recordings and their reference annotations of class activities are used to train an acoustic model[20].

1.2 The problem of data

The introduction of data-driven approaches for SED tasks is achieving great accuracy improvements as well as creating new challenges for the research community. In fact, training a model to perform this kind of task requires a lot of audio data with their relative annotations. The simple audio data collection process can already present some complexity to reach a representative distribution. As we mentioned in the previous section, the range of applications is very wide, which makes pretty hard to train a universal model to accomplish the task. This means that many datasets needs to be collected depending on the application field. Furthermore, we have also to consider the great diversity of sound characteristics that SED systems can face. A representative example is suggested by Mesaros et al. [20] and here reported:

..in the case of a dog barking class, this includes different instances of the source (different dogs), differences in the source state (for example mood), and environmental factors, such as the space where the source is

and what other sound sources are around and active, the location of the source, and the position of the microphone used to capture the sound.

All the audio data should be also paired with their relative annotations to provide class labels, onset, and offset of the events. We refer to this kind of data as *strong labels*. Generated strongly labeled data can be very difficult and costly and it is mostly human-based. In some cases, when a fast production of large quantities of training data is needed, SED systems can be also trained by adding *weak labels*, another kind of label that only contains the information about the presence of the event within the audio signal without specifying the temporal boundaries. An illustration of the two different types of labels is reported in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Strong and weak labels

Lastly, synthesizing the data can partially balance out the problem by taking advantage of automation, but it also presents some trade-offs. In fact, training SED models with a strongly labeled synthesized dataset could bring the model to overfit on a few sound examples [22].

1.3 Research questions

In the previous section, we described some of the challenges related to data collection and annotation for SED tasks. We can summarize the main aspects we mentioned with a few key points:

- SED systems need a considerable diversity in audio data characteristics to drive the acoustic model to a good generalization.
- Annotation process can be very costly.
- The use of synthetic data can introduce overfitting problems.

In this kind of context, data augmentation techniques could provide a solution for improving model generalization, balancing out a lack of strongly labeled data, and mitigating possible overfitting problems when using synthetic data.

Therefore, the main research questions of this study are following reported:

- What is the impact of audio data augmentation on Sound Event Detection?
- Can we combine together different techniques ?

These questions will lead this study that will address this topic starting from the next chapters.

1.4 Structure of the report

The report is structured as follows: Chapter 2 summarizes the state of the art and the most relevant related works. It also provides a brief introduction to the DCASE community. Chapter 3 describes the exploration of different DA techniques as well as the methodology and strategy that led the investigation. Results, conclusions and final comments are finally presented in Chapter 4.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

The chapter will present a quick overview regarding the most relevant studies related to this work including a quick historical introduction. The first section presents a short overview of the early approaches in SED task followed by an overview of the recent approaches based on deep learning. An introduction to the DCASE community is also provided, motivated by its remarkable contribution in improving the current state-of-the-art. Finally, a mention of the most relevant studies related to DA techniques for SED tasks is presented.

2.1 Early Approaches

Most of the early approaches to classify an audio signal into several target classes have been based on standard features such as mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs) and classifiers such as hidden Markov models (HMMs), Gaussian mixture models (GMMs) or Support Vector Machine (SVMs).

One of the first experiments has been presented in 2004 by Kennedy et al. [15] presenting a system based on a SVM classifier trained on (MFCCs) for the laughter detection in meetings. The system obtained a correct accept rate of 87% and a false alarm rate of 13%.

In 2006, Eronen et al. [10] published a very comprehensive study about the auto-

matic classification of 24 classes of everyday sounds. The system used MFCCs and their first-order time derivatives as features and tested different classifiers as HMMs, GMMs and a simple Neural Network (NN). The final evaluation was performed by human listeners who manually rated the outcome of the system. Two different experiments were performed and the averaged recognition accuracies of the computer system were 58% and 82% against the accuracies 69% and 88% obtained in the listening test for contexts and high-level classes, respectively.

Other valuable contributions to acoustic events detection were presented in 2008 in the *Computers in the Human Interaction Loop* (CHIL) project in their *Classification of Events, Activities, and Relationships* (CLEAR) evaluation [28]. The evaluation data consisted of overlapping acoustic events occurring in the CHIL lecture and meeting corpus. Participants to the CLEAR evaluation proposed 5 systems based on HMMs and one on SVMs; the best performing system used HMMs and AdaBoost for feature selection.

In 2010, a study conducted by Vavrek [35], took in consideration another SVM classifier for the classification of gunshot sounds showing SVMs quite reliable to accomplish the task.

2.2 Deep learning era

More recent approaches unify feature extraction with machine learning techniques to allow relevant features to be learnt automatically using deep neural networks (DNNs). They generally resolve the problem of computing the audio features relevant to a task. Their general structure includes multiple hidden layers with hidden units trained to represent some underlying structure in data [7]. After their success in auto-tagging [27][12], computer vision and speech recognition [30], DNNs have been also widely used for audio analysis tasks.

In 2016, Choi et al. [7], present a content-based automatic music tagging algorithm using fully convolutional neural networks (FCNs). The experiments showed that mel-spectrogram is an effective time-frequency representation for automatic tagging

and that more complex models benefit from more training data. Several works on sound events tasks have been mostly focused on sound event classification, especially using convolutional neural networks (CNN) [44] [25] [26] or recurrent neural networks (RNN) [37] [23].

In 2017, Cakir et al. [45] presented an exhaustive study about applying convolutional recurrent neural networks (CRNNs) for polyphonic sound event detection tasks. They combined the two approaches motivated by the capacity of the CNNs of extracting higher-level features that are invariant to local spectral and temporal variations, and the capability of RNNs in learning the longer-term temporal context in the audio signals. The results they observed validated the deep learning approach as a very promising method for polyphonic SED.

One of the potential limitations of the use of CNNs for sound event tasks comes from the location of the audio event that may only occur for a short time within the audio signal. This is quite different from image classification where the objects are usually centered and occupies a dominant part of the image, making the CNNs approach very effective. To balance out the issue, some attention models for audio classification have been experimented to attend to the audio events and ignore the background sounds [41].

In 2017, combining the previous methods, Xu et al. [42] presented a gated convolutional neural network and a temporal attention-based localization method for audio classification, which won the 1st place in the large-scale weakly supervised sound event detection task of Detection and Classification of Acoustic Scenes and Events (DCASE) 2017 challenge.

Another important contribution has been offered by the application of mean teacher models [33] to improve semi-supervised deep learning tasks. These models have been extensively experimented also on SED tasks [14] [9] and still represent the current model baseline of DCASE Task 4 2022.

2.3 DCASE Community

Detection and Classification of Acoustic Scenes and Events (DCASE) is a very fast-growing field of study that is more and more attracting the attention of several researchers in the last years. Starting from 2010 [29], several researchers responded to this growing interest by creating the DCASE Community. As highlighted in the official website [8], the community offers a platform for discussion of the different perspectives and approaches, from algorithm development to practical applications and their commercial value. Through this, it aims to support the development of computational scene and event analysis methods by providing public datasets and the opportunity to continuously compare different approaches on the same datasets, using consistent performance measures.

In 2013, the Community launched the first DCASE Challenge in collaboration with the Queen Mary University of London (QMUL). The aim of the initiative is to encourage the development of computational acoustic scene and event analysis methods, comparing different proposals using a common publicly available dataset [29]. The second edition of the Challenge was announced for 2016, including the organization of the first DCASE Workshop to provide a venue for researchers working on computational analysis of sound events and scene analysis to present and discuss their results. A timeline of the DCASE Community initiatives during the years is reported in Figure 3.

Figure 3: DCASE Challenges and Workshops timeline

2.3.1 DCASE Challenge 2022

The DCASE Challenge has been also renewed for 2022. Six different tasks have been published and offered to the research community. As addition contribution to this Master thesis, some experiments have been submitted as possible solution to the Task 4, focused on *Sound Event Detection in Domestic Environment*. The project has been submitted together with a technical report [3].

2.4 Related works on Data Augmentation

Data augmentation describes a set of techniques where copies of training instances are generated and used as additional training instances. This kind of approach has been widely applied in image processing task in the early recent. A canonical example of this is the presentation of rotated, scaled, and translated images in image classification. In summary, the intuition behind data augmentation is to enrich the sample distribution represented in training data to better approximate the population that will be sampled from during evaluation.

One of the most common fields of application of audio data augmentation is automatic speech recognition (ASR). A first application in speech recognition tasks was based in applying audio effects to spoken training examples. This typically took the form of adding noise, approximating reverberation or other channel effects. In 2017, for instance, a study conducted by Ko et al.[16] showed that combining clean and reverberated training data generates a considerable improvement in the close-talking scenario. Moreover, another study of 2018 by Liang et al.[17] on the ASR task, demonstrated that enforcing noise-invariant representations by penalizing differences between pairs of clean and noisy data can increase model accuracy, produce models that are robust to out-of-domain noise, and improve convergence speed. In 2017, Park et al. presented *SpecAugment* [24], a pretty straightforward approach that is still one of the most commonly used data augmentation methods right now. The suggested augmentation policy consisted of warping the features, masking blocks of frequency channels, and masking blocks of time step.

In 2021, Nam et al. [22], experimented SpecAugment on SED task. Their study also

applied several other DA techniques as frame-shift, mixup [43], and a new proposed method named *FilterAugment*. The results of the experiments showed the benefit of applying DA in SED tasks and suggested additional room for investigation.

Chapter 3

Experiment

This chapter will provide an introduction to the experiment including the applied methodology. The first section presents a brief overview of the model baseline together with the dataset used for model training and evaluation. A description of the different data augmentation techniques will be then presented in the following section. Finally, a description of the experiment methodology concludes the chapter.

3.1 Baseline architecture

Dataset and neural network baselines are both provided by DCASE committee and available on GitHub ¹.

Dataset

A *Development* and an *Evaluation* test sets are both provided by the committee. The *Development* dataset is composed by different splits of training data:

- Synthetic training set with strong annotations.
- Strong labeled training set.
- Weak labeled training set.

¹https://github.com/DCASE-REPO/DESED_task/tree/master/recipes/dcase2022_task4_baseline

- Unlabeled in domain training set.

The dataset includes real-world data coming from Audioset ² and synthetic data generated using Scraper [31]. Other sources are also included such as FUSS³ and FSD50K[11]. The *Evaluation* dataset is composed by YouTube public data annotated and available on Zenodo⁴. A complete description of the datasets is available on the 2021 DCASE Challenge website⁵. A summary of DCASE dataset is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: DCASE Dataset

Neural Network

The provided neural network baseline is the same as the DCASE 2021 Task 4 baseline and based on a Mean-Teacher model[9]. The Mean-Teacher model is a combination of two models: a student model and a teacher model, having the same architecture. The student model is the one used at inference while the goal of the teacher is to help the student model during training. The teacher’s weight are the exponential average of the student model’s weights. The models are a combination of a convolutional neural network (CNN) and a recurrent neural network (RNN) followed by an

²<https://research.google.com/audioset/>

³<https://github.com/google-research/sound-separation/tree/master/datasets/fuss>

⁴<https://zenodo.org/record/3588172#.Yw0Wg0xBzzc>

⁵<https://dcase.community/challenge2021/task-sound-event-detection-and-separation-in-domestic-environmental-audio-dataset>

attention layer. The output of the RNN gives strong predictions while the output of the attention layer gives the weak predictions [34]. Figure 5 shows an illustration of the baseline model.

Figure 5: Mean-teacher model

3.2 Data augmentation techniques

Data augmentation can be shortly described as a set of techniques to artificially increase the amount of data by manipulating existing data. Applied to audio data, it mainly consists in applying different digital signal processing techniques (DSP) either time or frequency based. Moreover, audio data manipulation can be either applied *offline* before model training by processing and storing the augmented data or in *real-time* during model training by applying data processing on-the-fly. For the purpose of our investigation, four different techniques have been explored and processed in real-time at model training time. The applied augmentation policies are briefly reported below together with their code implementation.

SpecAugment

SpecAugment is a data augmentation technique mostly applied on ASR tasks. In many of the recent approaches, the audio waveform is typically encoded as a visual representation such as a spectrogram [39]. This augmentation policy mainly consists of a frequency and time masking. As described by Park et al. [24], *SpecAugment*

modifies the spectrogram by warping it in the time direction, masking blocks of consecutive frequency channels, and masking blocks of utterances in time. These augmentations have been chosen to help the network to be robust against deformations in the time direction, partial loss of frequency information and partial loss of small segments of speech of the input. An example of such an augmentation policy is displayed below.

Figure 6: SpecAugment

```
def spec_augment(mels, time_mask_param, freq_mask_param):
    """SpecAugment data augmentation

    Args:
        mels: torch.tensor, mels spectrograms to process.
        time_mask_param (int): maximum possible length of the mask.
                               Indices uniformly
                               sampled from [0,
                               time_mask_param).
        freq_mask_param (int): maximum possible length of the mask.
                               Indices uniformly
                               sampled from [0,
                               freq_mask_param).

    Returns:
        torch.Tensor of augmented data
    """

    bsz, n_bands, frames = mels.shape
    tensors = []
```

```
for bindx in range(bsz):
    new_mels = mels[bindx]
    new_mels = torch.unsqueeze(new_mels, dim=0)

    masking = T.TimeMasking(time_mask_param=time_mask_param)
    new_mels = masking(new_mels)

    masking = T.FrequencyMasking(freq_mask_param=
                                   freq_mask_param)

    new_mels = masking(new_mels)
    tensors.append(torch.squeeze(new_mels, dim=0))

result = torch.stack(tensors)
return result
```

Convolution reverb

A Convolution Reverb is a very common reverberation technique used to emulate the reverberant behavior of a real acoustic space. It consists of a recorded sample, called Impulse Response (IR), of an acoustic space to excitation from a signal such as a sweep tone, starter gun, or snare drum crack, and the effect on the space of that signal after it has been removed and transformed by the convolution processor. Using the IR of a conference room, for instance, we can transform a clean speech sound as though it has been uttered in that room. An example of the described augmentation policy is displayed below.

Figure 7: Convolution reverb

```
def reverb(audio):
    """Convolutional reverb data augmentation

    Args:
        audio: torch.tensor, audio samples to process.
    Returns:
        torch.Tensor of augmented data
    """

    sample_rate = 16000
    rir_raw, _ = get_rir_sample(resample=sample_rate)

    rir = rir_raw[:, int(sample_rate * 1.01):int(sample_rate * 1.3)
                  ]

    rir = rir / torch.norm(rir, p=2)
    rir = torch.flip(rir, [1])
    rir = rir.cuda()
```

```

tensors = []
for i, _tensor in enumerate(audio):
    _tensor = _tensor.view(1, 160000)
    speech_ = torch.nn.functional.pad(_tensor, (rir.shape[1] -
                                                1, 0))
    augmented = torch.nn.functional.conv1d(speech_[None, ...],
                                           rir[None, ...])[0]

    tensors.append(augmented)

my_tensor = torch.stack(tensors, dim=1)
my_tensor = torch.squeeze(my_tensor)
return my_tensor

```

Background noise

Adding background noise to audio data is another common augmentation policy in audio tasks. It can simply implemented by adding a noise signal to the original audio data. A common method to adjust the intensity of noise is changing the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)[38].

$$SNR = \frac{P_{signal}}{P_{noise}} \quad (3.1)$$

$$SNR_{db} = 10 \log_{10} SNR \quad (3.2)$$

An example of the background noise augmentation policy is reported in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Background noise

```
def add_noise(mels, snrs=(6, 30), dims=(1, 2)):
    """Noise data augmentation

    Args:
        mels: torch.tensor, mels spectrograms to apply the white
            noise to.
        snrs: int or tuple, the range of snrs to choose from if
            tuple (uniform)
        dims: tuple, the dimensions for which to compute the
            standard deviation (
            default to (1,2) because
            assume
            an input of a batch of mel spectrograms.

    Returns:
        torch.Tensor of mels with noise applied
    """

    if isinstance(snrs, (list, tuple)):
```

```

    snr = (snrs[0] - snrs[1]) * torch.rand(
        (mels.shape[0],), device=mels.device
    ).reshape(-1, 1, 1) + snrs[1]
else:
    snr = snrs

snr = 10 ** (snr / 20) # linear domain
sigma = torch.std(mels, dim=dims, keepdim=True) / snr
mels = mels + torch.randn(mels.shape, device=mels.device) *
                    sigma

return mels

```

Mixup

Mixup augmentation policy has been recently experimented on SED tasks providing a considerable performance improvement [40]. In brief, this technique generates new synthetic samples using interpolation between two or more different samples. An augmented training example, for instance, can be constructed by using the following formula:

$$x_n = \alpha * x_i + (1 - \alpha) * x_j \quad (3.3)$$

$$y_n = \alpha * y_i + (1 - \alpha) * y_j \quad (3.4)$$

Where (x_i, y_i) and (x_j, y_j) are pairs of audio samples and α is the mix ratio. An example is provided in Figure 9 with $\alpha = 0.2$.

Figure 9: Mixup

```
def mixup(data, target=None, alpha=0.2, beta=0.2, mixup_label_type=
        "soft"):
    """Mixup data augmentation by permuting the data

    Args:
        data: input tensor, must be a batch so data can be permuted
            and mixed.
        target: tensor of the target to be mixed, if None, do not
            return targets.
        alpha: float, the parameter to the np.random.beta
            distribution
        beta: float, the parameter to the np.random.beta
            distribution
        mixup_label_type: str, the type of mixup to be used choice
            between {'soft', 'hard'}.

    Returns:
        torch.Tensor of mixed data and labels if given
    """
    with torch.no_grad():
        batch_size = data.size(0)
```

```
c = np.random.beta(alpha, beta)

perm = torch.randperm(batch_size)

mixed_data = c * data + (1 - c) * data[perm, :]
if target is not None:
    if mixup_label_type == "soft":
        mixed_target = torch.clamp(
            c * target + (1 - c) * target[perm, :], min=0,
            max=1
        )
    elif mixup_label_type == "hard":
        mixed_target = torch.clamp(target + target[perm, :], min=0, max=1)
    else:
        raise NotImplementedError(
            f"mixup_label_type: {mixup_label_type} not
            implemented.
            choice in "

            f"{'soft', 'hard'}"
        )

    return mixed_data, mixed_target
else:
    return mixed_data
```

Frame-shift

Frame-shift is a simple augmentation policy applied on spectrogram level. It mainly consists in shifting the audio frames within a specific time window. An example of the applied technique is following reported together the code baseline.

Figure 10: Frame-shift

```
def frame_shift(mels, labels, net_pooling=4):
    """Frame shift data augmentation

    Args:
        mels: torch.tensor, mels spectrograms to process.
        labels: sed labels

    Returns:
        torch.Tensor of mixed data and labels
    """

    bsz, n_bands, frames = mels.shape
    shifted = []
    new_labels = []
    for bindx in range(bsz):
        shift = int(random.gauss(0, 90))
        shifted.append(torch.roll(mels[bindx], shift, dims=-1))
        shift = -abs(shift) // net_pooling if shift < 0 else shift
        // net_pooling
        new_labels.append(torch.roll(labels[bindx], shift, dims=-1)
        )
    return torch.stack(shifted), torch.stack(new_labels)
```

3.3 Evaluation

Most of the SED systems have been often evaluated by using common methods such as conventional collar-based event decisions, event F-scores and event error rates. However, applied to SED tasks, these techniques have presented some limitations. In fact, they are not very efficient in taking into account several problems such as the subjective component within the human labeling task, data biases, or classification stability across sound classes. Moreover, classic methods are not very flexible to be tuned in order to match a variety of user experience requirements. In order to overcome the described limitations and to offer a better evaluation metric, a single polyphonic sound detection score (PSDS) has been presented in 2020 by Bilen et al. [4] who demonstrated the benefit of the suggested approach by re-evaluating the baseline and two of the top-performing systems from DCASE 2019 Task 4. Differently from other widely adopted metrics, PSDS offers three main improvements:

1. Introduces a new, flexible and robust definition of event detection that yields an evaluation closer to the end-user perception of sound events.
2. Discriminates cross-triggers from generic false positives and supports their custom weighting to cope with imbalanced datasets .
3. Evaluates the SED system performance using multiple operating points to truly measure the quality of the sound event modelling without system calibration bias.

The first point has been achieved by relaxing collar-based evaluation methods and introducing a flexible and more user-oriented definition of event detection. Two new parameters have been presented to describe, as a percentage, the intersection between two or more entities: *Detection Tolerance Criterion* (DTC) and *Ground Truth intersection Criterion* (GTC). Figure 11 shows the comparison between the two scenarios where the taller background rectangles are ground truths while the smaller foreground rectangles represent the system detection.

Figure 11: PSDC vs Collars

As mentioned in the second point, the PSDS takes also into account cross-trigger (CT) classes. In addition to true positives (TP) and false positives (FP) tracking, CTs represent the case in which the event temporary boundaries are correct despite the detected class being wrong. The event number 4 in Figure 12 represents an example of cross-trigger.

Figure 12: PSDC Cross-trigger

The implementation of algorithm is available online on the Audio Analytic GitHub repository ⁶. Furthermore, as already mentioned ⁶, the PSDC can be also tuned to meet different evaluation requirements. The evaluation of DCASE Task 4 has been

⁶https://github.com/audioanalytic/psds_eval

performed by using two different PSDS scores with different parameters as reported in Table 1.

Parameters	PSDS 1	PSDS 2
DTC	0.7	0.1
GTC	0.7	0.1
Cost of instability across class	1	0.3
Cost of CTs on user experience	0	0.5
Maximum False Positive rate	100	100

Table 1: PSDS parameter values

The first score better represents the system accuracy in terms of both class detection and time boundaries detection. The *PSDS 2* score, instead, increases the time boundaries detection tolerance and provides a better evaluation of class detection accuracy.

3.4 Experiment structure

As mentioned in paragraph 1.3, the goal of the experiment is to try to balance out the presence of synthetic data within a training set by enhancing the model’s generalization capacity via data augmentation techniques and, in particular, a combination of them. Task 4 of DCASE challenge 2022 has been selected as the scenario of the investigation. The experiment has been structured in three different phases where different models have been trained and evaluated against the a Development testset.

Phase 1

In this first step, seven different models have been trained. A first model without any data augmentation contribution has been trained and selected as the baseline for the evaluation. Other two models have been trained using Frame-shift and Convolutional Reverb augmentation policies as described in paragraph 3.2. Two additional

models have been also trained applying Mixup augmentation policy by setting the α parameter equal to 0.2 and 0.5. Finally, SpecAugment has been applied on two other models by setting *time_mask_param* and *freq_mask_param* parameters respectively to 80 and 120. All data augmentation models have been trained using a random activation policy λ to decide whether or not to process data augmentation:

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda \geq 0.5 & \quad \text{enable augmentation} \\ \lambda < 0.5 & \quad \text{disable augmentation} \end{aligned}$$

with λ in range [0-1]. A summary of the trained models is reported in Table 2,

Model ID	Augmentation policy	Activation policy
00	Baseline w/o d.a.	N/A
01	Reverb	λ
02	Frame-shift	λ
03	Mixup 0.2	λ
04	Mixup 0.5	λ
05	SpecAugment 80	λ
06	SpecAugment 120	λ

Table 2: Phase 1 - trained models

Phase 2

In the second phase, two additional models have been trained to evaluate the impact of combining two different augmentation policies. In both the new models, we applied two of the previous techniques by selecting the ones that performed better in phase 1. According to the final results reported in paragraph 4.1, *Mixup 0.2* and *SpecAugment 120* have been selected. In the first model, the activation policy λ has been applied to both augmentation techniques. This strategy potentially generates an overlap between the augmentation policies. Another activation policy γ has been defined to evaluate the second model avoiding the overlap between the two augmentation techniques:

$\gamma \geq 0.666$	enable <i>Mixup 0.2</i>
$\gamma \geq 0.333$ and $\gamma < 0.666$	enable <i>SpecAugment 120</i>
$\gamma < 0.333$	disable augmentation

with γ in range [0-1]. A summary of the trained models is reported in Table 3.

Model ID	Augmentation policy	Activation policy
07	Mixup 0.2 and SpecAugment 120	λ
08	Mixup 0.2 and SpecAugment 120	γ

Table 3: Phase 2 - trained models

Phase 3

As a last contribution to the experiment, the best model has been selected from the ones previously evaluated to be submitted for the DCASE challenge together with a brief technical report [3]. The submitted model is evaluated against the Evaluation testset by the DCASE committee and results are reported on the DCASE website ⁷.

⁷<https://dcase.community/challenge2022/>

Chapter 4

Results

The previous chapter has presented the methodology and the evaluation strategy applied to investigate the benefit of data augmentation for SED task with the presence of synthetic training data. In this last chapter, the outcome of the investigation will be presented together with a brief discussion about the results and future works.

4.1 Results and discussion

All the models described in 3.4 have been evaluated using the *PSDS 1* and *PSDS 2* scores introduced in 3.3. Full results are reported in Table 4.

Model ID	Augmentation policy	Activation policy	PSDS 1	PSDS 2
00	Baseline w/o d.a.	N/A	0.322	0.500
01	Reverb	λ	0.310	0.475
02	Frame-shift	λ	0.325	0.513
03	Mixup 0.2	λ	0.353	0.531
04	Mixup 0.5	λ	0.340	0.520
05	SpecAugment 80	λ	0.322	0.513
06	SpecAugment 120	λ	0.330	0.524
07	Mixup 0.2 and SpecAugment 120	λ	0.300	0.439
08	Mixup 0.2 and SpecAugment 120	γ	0.356	0.554

Table 4: Results

All the models have presented some slight improvements of the baseline except for the model *01*. This probably comes from the application of the convolutional reverb with only a single impulse response that did not benefit data generalization. Major improvements can be found in the *PSDS 2* scores, which can lead us to the assumption of more benefit coming from data augmentation in event class detection rather than event boundaries detection. Model *08* scored the best result validating the hypothesis of a benefit coming from combining data augmentation policy. However, considering the low gap from the baseline score, we can assume that data augmentation can only bring slight improvements in the overall SED task accuracy.

DCASE challenge result

Model *08* has been selected and submitted for the DCASE Challenge Task 4 evaluation. The model ranked thirty-two and forty-fourth out of fifty-two on the *PSDS 1* and *PSDS 2* scores. Full ranking is available on DCASE website ¹.

¹<https://dcase.community/challenge2022>

4.2 Future works

The presented work has presented a simple attempt to investigate the benefit in adopting multiple data augmentation techniques when training SED models. It validated some hypotheses and suggested several improvements as well. Some of the limitations of the current approach have been listed below together with some suggestions for further investigations.

- All the data augmentation techniques have been applied to the whole training set including real data. Considering the goal of balancing out the bias introduced by the use of synthetic data, further investigation would consider applying data augmentation only to synthetic data.
- For the aim of this investigation, only simple DSP techniques have been used. Further experiments could explore the combination of more advanced augmentation policies, such as *FilterAugment*[43], and experiment a wider range of parameters.
- Because of some computational constraints, only one single model has been trained for each augmentation strategy. This can potentially generate some not full reliable metrics due to some intrinsic variations that each model training can introduce. Further experiments should consider training multiple models with the same parameters in order to perform the evaluation on the average of the scores.

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